

Human Capital Pipelines – Antecedents and Consequences

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Abstract

Purpose

The paper aims to discuss the concept of human capital pipelines and explain how pipelines originate and the consequences of pipeline-based hiring in terms of labor market uncertainty, job embeddedness, social ties, homosocial reproduction, employee referrals, and turnover intent.

Design/methodology/approach

The author provides a viewpoint grounded on a review of recent research regarding human capital pipelines.

Findings

This paper aims at further developing our understanding of human capital pipelines and the implications of such practices. The author points out both the positive and negative aspects of pipeline-based hiring, with the hope that human resource practitioners and managers will adopt such practices based on the organization's strategic needs.

Originality/value

To date, very little conceptual and/or empirical work has been carried out on pipeline-based hiring. In organizations, it is important to understand how repeated hiring from labor sources can reduce labor market uncertainty regarding a job seeker's quality and potential productivity. However, it is also crucial to appreciate that such practices may have important pre and post hire implications for organizations and employees alike.

Keywords: Human capital pipelines; labor market uncertainty; homosocial reproduction; employee referrals; turnover intent

Human Capital Pipelines – Antecedents and Consequences

What are Human Capital Pipelines?

Human capital has long been considered a valuable resource that can lead to sustainable competitive advantage. Despite human capital being an important asset for organizations, acquisition of such resources from the labor market are fraught with information asymmetries. Organizations hire employees with the hope that they will be productive but there always exists the possibility of a mis-hire. When making a hiring decision, organizations strive their best to identify employees that would be a good fit to the job and the organization, but there is no guarantee that after hiring, employees will prove to be as valuable as initially assessed, or that they will be a good fit either with the job or the organization.

Signaling theory (Spence, 1974) has been widely used in the recruitment literature to explain the mechanism via which hiring firm evaluates and selects employees from the labor market based on observable signals of employee quality, such as personal history, education, employment record, etc. However, another mechanism by which hiring organizations can reduce uncertainty regarding applicant quality is through repeated interorganizational hiring, also known as ‘Human Capital Pipelines’ (Brymer, Molloy and Gilbert, 2014; Brymer et al., 2019). For example, a law firm in downtown Boston may repeatedly hire graduates from Suffolk University Law School. Development of these type of pipelines is largely time dependent, and if it is established that the human resources obtained from a particular labor source is proving to be reliable and productive, this should send positive signals to organizations that any future hire

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3 from that same source should also yield similar positive results. Over time this recruitment
4 strategy will become a part of the organizational learning process and as time elapses, the
5 repeated hiring pattern may even become routinized.
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11 Next, we will examine several antecedents of these human capital pipelines.
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13 14 **Antecedents of Human Capital Pipelines.** 15

16 17 *Homosocial Reproduction* 18

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20 The primary reasons behind pipeline-based hiring are to reduce search costs, and labor
21 market risks. Yet, certain managerial practices may also inadvertently lead to the creation of
22 specific pipelines over time. For example, the theory of homosocial reproduction suggests that
23 managers often display a tendency to extend employment offers to individuals whose social
24 status and background closely reflects that of the managers (Baron, 1984). Such hiring
25 preferences may become routinized, and managers may carry out selective hiring from certain
26 sources only (in this example it can be universities that promotes beliefs and values similar to
27 that of the manager's alma mater). With the passage of time, homosocial reproduction may lead
28 to the creation of a more homogenous unit and give rise to dominant coalitions within the
29 organization.
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45 However, the major problem associated with homosocial reproduction is that such
46 preferences typically reflect inherent managerial biases and as such may only be loosely
47 associated with actual productivity of the employees hired from select sources. Also, such biased
48 hiring practices may potentially reduce the heterogeneity of organizational human capital. Some
49 gender studies have highlighted homosocial reproduction in a negative light, investigating how
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3 individuals in organizations use their power to instill male-dominated power structures (Kanter,
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5 1977). Nevertheless, it is probable that managers may be prone to establishing pipelines with
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7 labor sources that reflect their own status and beliefs.
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10 11 *Employee Referrals* 12 13

14 One of the informal means by which organizations hire employees is employee referrals.
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16 When a vacant position is to be filled, managers often make their hiring decisions based on the
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18 recommendations of current employees, as such recommendations play a valuable role in
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20 reducing the uncertainty regarding the quality of a worker. Existing employees draw on their
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22 network ties to recommend prospective hires to their organizations - it could be a friend,
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24 someone who goes to the same club, a co-worker at a prior employer, a fellow graduate from the
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26 same university, etc. Current employees are also better positioned to provide realistic job
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28 information to prospective pipeline hires, which may play an important role in the job seeker's
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30 decision to accept employment.
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36 While employee referrals may not directly influence the pipeline creation process, over
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38 time it may play an indirect but significant role in assisting managers identify valuable labor
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40 sources. If the referred hire proves to be productive and of good quality, and does not show
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42 intent of quitting during the initial employment period, such positive signals may encourage
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44 managers to rely more on hiring through referrals in the future. As such, if the referred
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46 employees have shared a common labor source in the past (alma mater, for instance), managers
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48 may quickly come to associate employee quality with a particular labor source and might
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50 develop a predisposition towards hiring employees exclusively from that source, creating a
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52 pipeline between the organization and the labor source.
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Consequences of Pipeline Based Hiring

Reduced Turnover

A popular dilemma faced by organizations is that human resources are not considered to be organizational property and can be easily lost when employees leave. Highly valued individuals may choose to leave the organization at any time they wish and consequently, organizations have to spend considerable time and resources in rehiring and retraining employees. However, employees hired via pipelines may exhibit lower turnover intentions.

The concept of job embeddedness can potentially explain why pipeline employees will be less willing to look for opportunities elsewhere. Job embeddedness suggest that the greater number of formal or informal connections an employee has with other members of the organization, the less likely is the employee to leave (Mitchell et al., 2001). As organizations continue hiring from certain labor sources, the human capital at the firm should become more homogenous and this should strengthen the social ties between 'similar' employees. The creation of close relationships among similar co-workers should make employees more dependent on each other and decrease their propensity of quitting.

In the case of prospective employees, the creation of pipelines benefits job seekers by familiarizing them in advance of the organization's cultures and task environment via the social ties between the job seekers and the labor source alumni already employed at the organization (Brymer, Molloy and Gilbert, 2014). Many of the formal and informal routines and processes will be made known to the candidates by the labor source alumni, even before the candidates come to work at the organization. It is also quite probable that after hiring, pipeline employees will receive greater support from their labor source alumni in terms of development and

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3 integration compared to hires from the general labor market, thus allowing pipeline hires to
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5 assimilate faster to the firm's culture. All these dynamics should have a positive impact on a
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7 pipeline hire's initial and subsequent performance, increasing job satisfaction and lowering
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9 turnover intent.
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11 12 13 *Increased Costs* 14 15

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17 Despite its benefits, pipeline-based hiring can incur additional costs for an organization.
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19 For instance, organizations want to appropriate most of the value associated with an employee's
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21 labor and services, and this is particularly possible when the employee has less knowledge about
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23 the actual value of his/her contributions. However, in the case of pipeline hires, employees
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25 should have better information regarding their relative worth. To elaborate:
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30 (i) Pipelines are established when organizations identify and subsequently hire
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32 repeatedly from labor sources that supply productive employees. This suggests
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34 that pipeline hires will likely be aware that they are of better quality than other
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36 general labor market hires, and this may give them relatively higher bargaining
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38 power when it comes to negotiating salaries and benefits.
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40 (ii) Pipeline hires (because of their access to internal information through social ties)
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42 will also be able to make better assessments regarding appropriate remuneration
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44 levels by comparing themselves with the labor source alumni working at the
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46 organization. This too may result in pipeline employees having significantly
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48 higher negotiating power compared to their external labor market counterparts.
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Conclusion

Typically, organizations rely on market signals of productivity to determine quality of potential employees prior to hiring. Repeated interorganizational hiring is another mechanism by which organizations mitigate uncertainty and risks related to labor market hires. Although pipeline-based hiring is a common organizational phenomenon, to date little theoretical and empirical advancements have been made on the topic. This paper highlights both the benefits and costs of establishing human capital pipelines and aims to serve as a valuable theoretical and practical guideline for researchers and practitioners alike.

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